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OPTIMIZING BIOGAS PRODUCTION THROUGH ANAEROBIC DIGESTION OF DIFFERENT BIOMASS RESIDUES

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Energy is the lifeblood of human civilization, an invisible force that powers our homes, fuels our industries, and drives the progress of society. Without access to dependable and cost-effective energy sources, both communities and individuals encounter substantial obstacles in fulfilling their fundamental requirements. However, as the world is facing a growing energy demand as populations increase and economies develop, there is a rising need for reliable and affordable energy sources. However, traditional methods like fossil fuel combustion contribute to climate change and environmental degradation. (International Energy Agency, 2021). In the context of the Philippines, the country's energy supply is heavily reliant on fossil fuels, particularly coal, which is expected to decline over time due to depletion of resources. According to the Philippine Energy Plan 2017-2040, the share of coal in the country's energy mix is expected to decline from around 45% in 2020 to around 30% by 2040 (DOE, 2019).

With this, biomass residue is an organic material that are no longer needed for their original purpose and are considered waste that gained increasing attention as a potential source of renewable energy production due to its abundant availability and potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (EUBIA, 2019). Based on the report by Department of Energy (2019), Philippines generates around 14.3 million metric tons (MT) of biomass waste annually. In connection to this, agriculture industry is one of the major contributor of the biomass waste that generated around 46.3 million metric tons (MT) that includes crop residues, animal manure, and other agricultural by-products, followed by 24.4 million (MT) of municipal waste that collected in household, commercial, and institutional waste as well as 15.5 million (MT) of industrial waste obtained from various industrial processes, such as manufacturing, mining, and construction which poses environmental and health risk especially if its remain untapped and neglected. Despite the widespread availability and unlimited access to biodegradable biomass as a potential source of biogas, the production of bioenergy presents significant challenges due to the lack of viable technologies for large-scale consumption, especially in rural areas. This is noteworthy considering that biogas, derived from the anaerobic digestion of organic matter, holds promise as a renewable and sustainable energy source. However, the inadequacy of suitable technologies and infrastructure in rural areas acts as a substantial barrier to the

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widespread adoption of biogas as a viable energy source. Consequently, many rural communities continue to rely on traditional and often hazardous methods of cooking and heating which can result in health issues, increased expenses, and environmental difficulties.

Thus, this study aims to utilize the different biomass residue as an alternative source of biogas energy through anaerobic digestion and evaluate its other potential use in sustaining energy production.

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